

3D WOVEN COMPOSITES FOR ENERGY ABSORBING APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Due to the presence of through-thickness reinforcement, 3D woven composites have superior fracture toughness, fatigue life, and damage tolerance compared to laminated composites. Furthermore, 3D woven composites exhibit a progressive damage behavior which is more benign than the typical catastrophic failure behavior of laminated composites. These properties lead to high specific energy absorption (SEA); making 3D woven composite parts suitable lighter weight replacements to those manufactured using traditional materials such as laminated composites or high-strength metals. The goal of this study was to demonstrate these characteristics by comparing the performance of a 3D woven composite beam loaded in three-point bending to that of a similar beam made from high-strength steel (HSST). This was achieved by taking a combined experimental and simulation approach for both materials. Constant cross-section 3D woven composite beams were manufactured for this study using an aerospace grade carbon fiber and toughened epoxy resin. The composite beams and vehicle side intrusion beams made of HSST were tested in three-point bending quasi-statically. Both experiments were modeled at the macro-scale, i.e. continuum level, with nonlinear finite element models that captured progressive failure and crushing behavior for the composite beam and the plasticity of the metal beam. The experimentally validated HSST material properties were then used to simulate the load-displacement behavior of a constant cross-section HSST beam that had an adjusted thickness to match the peak load of the composite beam. The results of the study showed that the 3D woven composite beam designed to carry the same peak load of a HSST beam has 37% higher SEA under three-point bending.

1 INTRODUCTION

3D woven composites have superior fracture toughness, fatigue life, and damage tolerance compared to laminated composites due to the presence of through-thickness reinforcement [1]-[6]. These properties lead to high specific energy absorption (SEA) of 3D woven composites, enabling the manufacturing of parts suitable to replace the traditional high-strength metal ones used in the aerospace and automotive industries, at a lighter weight. In addition, 3D weaving technology allows for the tailoring of the reinforcement architecture and fiber content to meet performance requirements and also produces a preform woven in a near-final shape, reducing complexity and cost of manufacturing [7]. Indeed, three-dimensional woven composites are being adopted in aerospace for critical applications due to their tailored strength and impact resistance [8]. While the cost of fibers and resins used for aerospace applications can be prohibitive, it has been demonstrated by the BMW i3 and i8 that the cost of fiber and resin can be brought down to levels suitable for automotive applications [9].

Occupant safety is a key design driver in today's automobiles. Due to the short design cycle times and cost of physical testing, full and partial vehicle crash simulation models are used extensively by automotive OEMs. Thus, the introduction of a new material into a vehicle design requires that it can be modeled in such crash simulations. Although a large amount of work has been done on predicting and modeling the failure behavior of traditional laminated composites, this still proves to be a challenging task [10]. For 3D woven composites, progressive failure modeling efforts have been

primarily limited to the meso-scale which is computationally expensive [11] and provides a level of detail higher than what is required for typical structural analysis of components and assemblies. A recent study by the authors features a macro-scale progressive failure material model developed for 3D woven composites, but it is validated only for quasi-static load cases [12].

The overall goal of this study was to evaluate the energy absorption characteristics of 3D woven composites for automotive crash structures. The specific objectives were to: 1) experimentally characterize the performance of two side intrusion beams: a high-strength steel (HSST) beam with an optimized geometry from an actual vehicle and a 3D woven composite beam with a constant cross-section geometry, 2) demonstrate the ability to simulate the nonlinear force-displacement response of these experiments, and 3) simulate the behavior of a constant cross-section HSST to provide a direct comparison of energy absorption characteristics with the 3D woven composite.

Figure 1: Experimental setup of 3-point bending test of the high-strength steel (HSST) and 3D woven composite beams. The cross-sectional geometry details shown are for the composite beam.

Figure 2: Photographs showing the 3D composite beam 3-point bending experiments: (a) at the beginning of testing, and (b) after complete failure. The composite beam was not painted and therefore the carbon fiber and near white resin are clearly visible.

2 MATERIALS & METHODS

2.1 Experimental Setup

In order to characterize the load carrying and energy absorption capabilities of the optimized geometry HSST beam and the constant cross-section 3D woven composite beam, quasi-static, 3-point bending tests were conducted (Figures 1, 2 & 3). While this test is simple, it represents the basic characteristics of a side impact test. The constant cross-section design for the composite beam shown in Figure 1 was chosen as a low cost solution which compromises weight savings for reduced manufacturing cost. All beams were tested to failure using a hydraulic test system under displacement control quasi-statically at a rate of 8 mm/s. The force-displacement curve and maximum load were

recorded for each sample tested. Three samples were tested for each material and all beams were weighed before testing.

The HSST beam sample used in this study was a side intrusion beam taken from a high-volume production vehicle. This beam was manufactured by hot stamping an approximately 2mm thick sheet of high-strength steel such as BTR165. This beam had a geometry optimized for the vehicle side-impact event which in this study was represented simply as the 3-point bending test (Figure 3).

The 3D woven composite beams tested in this study were manufactured by Albany Engineered Composites (AEC) using aerospace grade materials. These beams had a constant cross-section and their design was only optimized to match the initial stiffness of the HSST beam. The preforms were woven using Hexcel IM7 48K carbon fiber yarns on a computer controlled 3D Jacquard weaving loom. The fiber architecture chosen was a ply-to-ply design tailored to have 60% of the fiber in the warp direction and a 60% fiber volume fraction. The objective of this distribution of warp/weft fiber was to improve the stiffness and strength of the beam along its length, i.e. the warp direction. The weave design and program code generation were completed using AEC's proprietary software Techniweaver™. The parts were molded through resin transfer molding (RTM) using Cycom PR520 toughened epoxy resin.

Finally, in order to calibrate material properties used in the macro-scale FEA models, tensile test coupons were extracted from both the steel and composite beams.

Figure 3: Photographs showing the high-strength steel (HSST) beam after testing. The optimized geometry takes advantage of the ductility of the material and the beam deforms in a way that maximizes the load carrying capacity and energy absorption.

2.2 FEA Modeling

The geometry of the HSST beam was obtained through 3D laser scanning of the actual beam before testing. This geometry was then meshed in Abaqus/CAE using 4-noded shell elements with reduced integration (S4R). The HSST material was modeled using a metal plasticity model using material properties that were obtained from the coupon testing. The impactor and supports were modeled as half-cylinders using 4-noded rigid elements. Frictionless contact was assumed between the beam, supports, and impactor. The impactor was displaced 100mm downward from its initial position touching the beam, through imposed displacement using an amplitude curve which ramps up the displacement smoothly. A quasi-static analysis was run using the explicit dynamic procedure in Abaqus/Explicit with mass scaling to increase stable time increments and reduce total computation time. The displacement and vertical reaction force at the impactor reference node were used for post-processing.

The finite-element model of the 3D woven composite beam similarly consisted of 4-noded shell elements with reduced integration (S4R) to model the composite beam throughout the span, with the exception of the region underneath the impactor where failure is predicted to take place (Figure 4). In that region, a finer mesh comprised of 8-noded continuum-shell elements was used, with 6 elements through the thickness. Shell-to-solid coupling was used to couple neighboring elements of different topologies. A nonlinear crushing material model with failed element deletion was used in the region underneath the impactor [12]. This material model was implemented as a user subroutine in Abaqus, and the parameters used were chosen based on a combination of existing empirical data and test data

(elastic modulus and ultimate tensile strength) for coupons obtained from the beams manufactured for this study. The impactor, supports, and quasi-static analysis definition for the 3D woven composite beam were modeled similarly to the HSST beam as described above.

In the absence of a 3D woven composite beam design optimized for the 3-point bending load case, a constant cross-section steel beam FEA model was used to create a basis for comparison of energy absorption characteristics of the two materials. This constant cross-section steel beam had the same geometry as the composite beam, but the material thickness was adjusted to match the peak load of the composite beam.

Figure 4: FEA model of the 3-point bending test setup. The inset shows mesh detail and σ_{11} distribution in continuum-shell elements (Abaqus SC8R) under the impactor region.

Figure 5: Stress plot of FEA model for the optimal geometry high-strength steel (HSST) beam in fully deformed state.

3 RESULTS

Stress contour plots of 3D woven composite and HSST beam FEA models are shown in Figures 4 and 5, respectively. Force-displacement curves from the 3-point bending experiments and FEA simulations are shown in Figure 6. Very little scatter was observed between the three samples tested, hence, only one representative curve for the optimized HSST and constant cross-section 3D woven composite beam are shown in Figure 6. The three FEA curves presented in Figure 6 correspond to the optimized HSST beam, the constant cross-section HSST beam, and the constant cross-section 3D woven composite beam.

The mass, maximum loads and energy absorption measures from the experiments and FEA simulations are presented in Table 1. The energy absorbed for each case was calculated using the area under the force-displacement curve.

The optimized geometry HSST beam exhibited significant deformations near the center of the beam under the impactor both experimentally and in the FEA model (Figures 3 & 5). These deformations occur in such a manner that increase the cross-sectional inertia of the beam and improve the beam's ultimate load carrying capability. This can be observed as the outer edges of the central portion of the beam curl to form channels on the outer edges as the beam is deformed.

For both materials, the FEA model predicted force-displacement curves show very close correlation to the experimental results (Figure 6) which validates the modeling methods and material models used. While the stiffness of the constant cross-section 3D woven composite matched the

optimized HSST beam, its peak load was 23% lower (Table 1). The constant cross-section HSST beam analysis predicted a maximum load within 7% of the 3D woven composite beam it was designed to match. While the constant cross-section HSST beam absorbed 13% more energy than the 3D woven composite, it was 27% less efficient when normalized by mass.

Figure 6: Comparison of five force-displacement curves for experiments and FEA models.

Label	Mass of beam [kg]	Maximum Force [kN]	Energy absorbed up to 100 mm [J]	Energy Absorbed / Mass [J/kg]
Constant Cross Section – 3D Composite – Experiment	1.30	11.6	604	464
Constant Cross Section – 3D Composite – FEA	1.23	11.2	622	504
Optimized – HSST – Experiment	1.65	15.0	1044	633
Optimized – HSST – FEA	1.65	15.2	1023	619
Constant Cross Section – HSST – FEA	1.92	12.0	705	367

Table 1: Mass, maximum force and energy absorption values for experiments and FEA models.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The main goal of this study was to study the energy absorption characteristics of 3D woven composites for automotive crash structure applications. A combined experimental and computational approach was used to compare the performance of beams made of 3D woven composite and high-strength steel (HSST) in a 3-point bending load-case which was chosen as a simplified substitute for a side impact event. Overall, the results show that 3D woven composites have higher SEA than HSST and can facilitate weight reduction in vehicles if utilized in crash structures (Table 1).

The geometry of the beam is a critical consideration. When the optimized geometry of the actual HSST side intrusion beam was replaced with the constant cross-section geometry of the 3D composite beam, its efficiency in energy absorption dropped by 42%. This underscores the importance of the structure in specific energy absorption measurements [13]. In the absence of an optimized geometry 3D woven composite beam for comparison, this approach was chosen to provide a comparison between the materials. It is conceivable that exploitation of the deformation and energy absorption characteristics of different materials will result in significantly different designs.

The force-displacement curves for the FEA models closely correlated with the experimental results in both the progression of failure and the overall response (Figure 6). While modeling highly nonlinear load-cases like this for metals is well understood and quite straightforward, the results demonstrate that similar analyses can also be performed for 3D woven composite materials that have a more complex progressive failure behavior [12].

Future work includes building on this study to further refine the design of the 3D woven composite beam for increased efficiency. In addition, a more direct characterization of the SEA of 3D woven composites under high-rate dynamic crushing loads will be carried out. This will be studied in a manner similar to coupon testing, and not as a component test in order to minimize the structural contribution to the SEA [13].

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